

Plant species Diversity in Salu Reserved Forest, East Bago Yoma, Bago Township

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Abstract

The present study deals with the assessment of plant species diversity, 28 quadrats (20m x 20m each) were set up and observed. A total of 126 tree species representing 79 genera and 43 families were recorded. In this study, Thit Phyu area occupied higher value of species richness, evenness and had a higher combined diversity index than Seik Phu Taung area in tree and shrub layers. (i.e. Shannon-Wiener and Simpson's indices). Coefficient of similarity value were 66.667%, 66.321% and 72.131% in tree, shrub, and herb layers of two different sites by using Sorenson index, 1948. Ecological successful species with the highest important value were *Melanorrhoea glabra* Wall. (33.386%) in Thit Phyu area and *Sapium insigne* Benth. (26.743%) in Seik Phu Taung area. The highest basal area of 6.710 m²/ha and 5.505 m²/ha (≥ 211 cm GBH) had been recorded in both sites of study area. Tree distribution by height class intervals showed that 36.629% of tree individuals are belonging to ≤ 6 m category. All recorded data will continue to provide valuable information for management and biodiversity conservation in future.

Keywords: Species diversity, species richness, evenness, Importance Value Index (IVI) and Frequency class.

Introduction

The increasing potential threat to biological diversity is an irreversible environmental disorder that warrants immediate remedial measures for sustainable management and conservation of biodiversity. Species diversity reflects species richness and evenness, and expresses differences of community structure, community composition, and community habitat conditions.

The variations in species diversity can be linked to several ecological gradients. The change of non-alive condition (e.g., climate, soil and temperature) affects species composition and distribution. Moreover, species diversity is affected by multi-environmental factors. Tree species diversity in tropical areas varies greatly from place to place mainly due to variation in biogeography, habitat and disturbance. (Whitmore, 1998). Quantitative inventories help in identification of economically useful species as well as species of special concern, i.e. rare, uncommon and vulnerable species. (Keel, 1993). Information on the distribution and abundance of tree species is of primary importance in the planning and implementation of biodiversity conservation. The diversity of trees is fundamental to total rainforest biodiversity, because trees provide resources and habitat structure for almost all other rainforest species. (Cannon, 1998). Present study aims to stratify the forest vegetation into different forest area and to analyze species diversity, evenness, similarity parameters, and diameter and height class distribution.

Study Area

Salu Reserved Forest is situated in East Bago Yoma, Bago Township. This area is located between 17° 04' N to 17° 50' N latitudes and 96° 24' E to 96° 41' E Longitudes. Total area of Salu reserved forest is 25,449ha.

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Thit Phyu Area

It is located at elevation between 25-73m and lies in the interior part of Salu Reserved Forest. Topography is slightly slope to flatten area.

Seik Phu Taung Area

It is located at elevation between 18-84m and lies in upper part of the Salu Reserved Forest. Its topography is slope to deeply slope.

Fig 1. Location Map of Study Area

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Source: Forest Department, Bago Township

Fig 2. Salu Reserved Forest Area, Bago Township

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Fig. 3. Monthly mean temperature of Bago Township in year 2007-2010

Source: Department of Meteorology and Hydrology, Bago Township

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Fig. 4. Monthly mean rainfall of Bago Township in year 2007-2008

Source: Department of Meteorology and Hydrology, Bago Township

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Fig. 5. Monthly mean humidity of Bago Township in year 2007-2008

Source: Department of Meteorology and Hydrology, Bago Township

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Climate

Minimum and maximum mean temperature range varies from 23.7 °C to 33.8 °C in 2009 and 23.7 °C to 33.8 °C in 2010 also. The monthly mean rainfall ranges from 0 mm to 59 mm in 2009 and 0 mm to 378 mm in 2010. Moreover, the monthly mean relative humidity ranges from 51% to 81% in 2009 and 42% to 88% in 2010. The climate of study area is tropical monsoon climate.

Data Collection

Field data were conducted during December, 2010 to January, 2011 by using 20 x 20m (a total of 28 quadrats) for trees. All the plots were systematically surveyed for all trees ≥ 10 cm diameter at breast height (GBH). To account overall species diversity two subplots 5x5m (for shrubs), four subplots 1x1m (for herbs) were laid down in the plot. (Santra, 1999)

Fig.6. Layout for the study of a forested area by quadrat method

The spatial location (latitude, longitude and altitude) of each plot was measured by using a Global Positioning System (GPS). Species identification was performed by the use of literatures cited in key to the families of the flowering plants (YU, 1994), Backer et al., (1963), and Kress et al. (2003) and matching with herbarium specimen in Department of Botany, University of Yangon.

Data Analysis

The collected field data were analysed for Jackknife estimate of species richness (Heltsh & Foerster, 1983), number of species diversity (Shannon-Wiener and Simpson indices, 1963) and evenness (Shannon-Wiener function, 1963). Similarity of floristic composition between two different study sites was determined by Sorenson's index of similarity, 1948. To study the quantitative analysis, the Importance Value Index (IVI) for the tree species was determined as the sum of the relative values of frequency, density and dominance (Curtis and McIntosh, 1950). Species frequency distribution was studied with five frequency classes of Raunkiaer (1934). Population density of tree species were analyzed across through fixed GBH classes and height class intervals.

Results

Table 1. Number of families, genera and species of all strata in different study sites

Taxonomic rank	Thit Phyu Area			Seik Phu Taung Area		
	Trees	Shrubs	Herbs	Trees	Shrubs	Herbs
Family	41	47	48	38	39	32
Genera	74	87	80	73	72	72
Species	103	105	99	86	88	84

Fig 7. Number of families, genera and species of all strata in different study sites

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Table 2. Consolidated detail of species inventory in Salu Reserved Forest

Description	Thit Phyu area			Seik Phyu Taung Area		
	Trees	Shrubs	Herbs	Trees	Shrubs	Herbs
No of Sample Plot	14	28	56	14	28	56
No of Species	103	105	99	86	88	84
No of Individual	789	1089	1435	810	1026	1320
Unique Species	29	18	16	27	17	17
Species Richness	103.117	105.520	99.736	86.135	88.539	84.736
Species Evenness	0.842	0.700	0.825	0.789	0.929	0.773
Shannon-Wiener diversity index (H')	5.631	4.700	5.471	5.071	5.352	4.943
Simpson diversity index (D)	0.958	0.919	0.963	0.942	0.959	0.936

Diversity

In this study, the tree layer of Thit Phyu area had a diversity index (5.631, 0.958) and that of Seik-Phu Taung area had (5.071, 0.942) by the method of Shannon-Wiener's (H) and Simpson's diversity index (D) respectively. Evenness of tree layer in Thit Phyu area (0.842) was relatively higher than that of Seik Phu Taung area (0.789). The shrub layer of Thit Phyu area had diversity index (4.700, 0.919) and that of Seik Phu Taung area had also (5.352, 0.959). The evenness of the shrub layer in Thit Phyu area (0.700) is lower than that of Seik Phu Taung area (0.929). Similarly, the diversity index of herb layer in Thit Phyu area had (5.471, 0.963) and that of Seik Phu Taung area had also (4.943, 0.936). (Table 2)

Table-3. Coefficient of similarity in Thit Phyu Area and Seik Phu Taung Area

Layer	No of Species	Identical Species	Sorenson's Coefficient of similarity (K_s)
Trees	189	63	66.667%
Shrubs	193	64	66.321%
Herbs	183	66	72.131%

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The result of coefficient of similarity showed that herb layer had high similarity (coefficient value 72.131%) follow by tree layer (coefficient value 66.667%) and shrub layer (66.321%) between the two different study area. (Table 3)

Table-4. Ranking Important Value Index of Tree Species in Thit Phyu Area

No	Scientific Name	Family	Common Name	R.D (%)	R.F (%)	R.Dm (%)	IVI (%)
1	<i>Melanorrhoea glabra</i> Wall.	Anacardiaceae	Thit-si	5.450	4.333	21.602	31.386
2	<i>Phlebocalyma lobbiana</i> Mast.	Olacaceae	Wun-the-gye	15.970	2.333	1.966	20.269
3	<i>Nephelium hypoleucum</i> Kurz.	Sapindaceae	Taw-kyet-mauk	1.267	1.333	10.617	13.217
4	<i>Pithecellobium lobatum</i> Benth.	Mimosaceae	Danyin	4.056	2.667	3.976	10.698
5	<i>Kayea nerrosa</i> T. Anders.	Guttiferae	Taung-gangaw	2.915	3.000	4.401	10.316
6	<i>Ochna</i> sp.	Ochnaceae	Myauk-min-thewege	3.676	1.667	4.000	9.342
7	<i>Swintonia floribunda</i> Griff.	Anacardiaceae	Taung-tha-yet	2.408	3.000	3.114	8.523
8	<i>Sapium insigne</i> Benth.	Euphorbiaceae	Taung-kala	2.535	2.333	2.846	7.715
9	<i>Ochna wallichii</i> Planch.	Ochnaceae	Indaing-seni	2.535	2.333	2.729	7.597
10	<i>Syzygium grande</i> (W.t) Walp.	Myrtaceae	Tha-bye-ywet-gyi	1.774	2.667	2.297	6.738
.	.	.	Others	57.414	74.333	42.529	174.277
.	.	.	Total	100	100	100	300

Fig-8. Ranking Important Value Index of Tree Species in Thit Phyu Area

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Table-5. Ranking Important Value Index of Tree Species in Seik Phu Taung Area

No	Scientific Name	Family	Common Name	R.D (%)	R.F (%)	R.Dm (%)	IVI (%)
1	<i>Sapium insigne</i> Benth.	Euphorbiaceae	Taung-kala	13.407	4.626	8.710	26.743
2	<i>Phlebocalyma lobbiana</i> Mast.	Olacaceae	Wun-the-gye	15.498	4.982	1.923	22.403
3	<i>Dialium indum</i> Linn.	Caesalpinaceae	Taung-kha-ye	4.428	3.915	7.039	15.382
4	<i>Kayea nerrosa</i> T. Anders.	Guttiferae	Taung-gangaw	3.444	3.203	6.500	13.147
5	<i>Syzygium grande</i> (W.t) Walp.	Myrtaceae	Tha-bye-ywet-gyi	1.722	3.559	7.712	12.993
6	<i>Manglietia insignis</i> Blume.	Magnoliaceae	Taung-sa-ga	0.984	1.779	8.798	11.562
7	<i>Sterculia foetida</i> Linn.	Sterculiaceae	Let-kok	2.337	1.423	6.583	10.343
8	<i>Ochna</i> sp.	Ochnaceae	Myauk-min-thwe-gye	3.198	2.491	4.347	10.036
9	<i>Melanorrhoea glabra</i> Wall.	Anacardiaceae	Thit-si	1.599	1.423	6.510	9.532
10	<i>Antidesma velutinum</i> Tulasne.	Euphorbiaceae	Kin-ba-lin	4.059	3.915	0.430	8.403
.	.	.	Others	49.323	68.683	41.455	159.462
.	.	.	Total	113	114	112	339

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Fig-9. Ranking Important Value Index of Tree Species in Seik Phu Taung Area

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Important Value Index of Tree Species

The tree layer in Thit Phyu area was dominated by *Melanorrhoea glabra* Wall. (Thit-si) with the highest IVI of 31.386, second most dominant species was *Phlebocalyma lobbiana* Mast. (Wun-the-gye) (IVI = 20.269%) and *Nephelium hypoleucum* Kurz. (Taw-kyet-mauk) was third (IVI = 13.217%). (Table 4, Fig 8) The tree layer in Seik Phu Taung area was dominated by *Sapium insigne* Benth.(Taung-kala) with the highest IVI of 26.743, second most dominant species was *Phlebocalyma lobbiana* Mast. (Wun-the-gye) (IVI = 22.403%) and *Dialium indum* Linn. (Taung-kha-ye) was third (IVI = 15.382 %). (Table 5, Fig 9)

Table (6) Horizontal structure of tree species across GBH class interval

DBH Class (cm)	Thit Phyu Area			Seik Phu Taung Area		
	Total BA (m)	BA/ha (m ² ha ⁻¹)	Tree/ha	Total BA (m)	BA/ha (m ² ha ⁻¹)	Tree/ha
≤ 30	1.004	0.896	335	0.073	0.065	366
31-60	0.512	0.457	194	0.512	0.457	162
61-90	1.381	1.233	96	1.325	1.183	88
91-120	1.963	1.753	32	2.110	1.884	49
121-150	2.498	2.230	28	2.759	2.463	31
151-180	0.633	0.565	3	1.568	1.400	9
181-210	2.437	2.176	9	2.411	2.153	9
≥ 211	7.515	6.710	9	6.166	5.505	10
Total	17.943	16.021	704	16.924	15.111	723

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Fig.10. Horizontal structure of tree species across GBH class interval in Thit Phyu Area

Fig.11. Horizontal structure of tree species across GBH class interval in Seik Phu Taung Area

Horizontal structure of tree species across GBH class interval

GBH class of ≤ 30 cm was the smallest contribution in total basal area (1.004, 0.703) and GBH class of ≥ 211 possessed largest contribution in basal area (7.515, 6.166) of both study sites.

In the present study, the highest basal area of $6.710 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}$ and $5.505 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}$ (≥ 211 cm GBH) had been recorded in both sites of study area. The density of trees per hectare for Thit Phyu and Seik Phu Taung forests area was 704 and 723 respectively, which was high in comparison to the above studies. (Table 6, Fig. 10,11)

Table (7) Population density of tree species across GBH class interval

DBH Class (cm)	Thit Phyu Area			Seik Phu Taung Area		
	Species	Individual	% of Individual	Species	Individual	% of Individual
≤ 30	68	375	47.529	55	410	50.617
31-60	66	217	27.503	52	181	22.346
61-90	51	107	13.561	34	98	12.099
91-120	24	36	4.563	28	55	6.790
121-150	13	31	3.929	19	35	4.321
151-180	3	3	0.380	6	10	1.235
181-210	7	10	1.267	8	10	1.235
≥ 211	7	10	1.267	6	11	1.358
Total	103	789	100	86	810	100

Fig.12. Population Density of tree species across GBH class interval in Thit Phyu Area

Fig.13. Population density of tree species across GBH class interval in Seik Phu Taung Area

Population density of tree species across GBH class interval

In the GBH class of ≤ 30 cm, population density of tree species found that 47.529% of individuals in Thit Phyu area and 50.617% of individuals in Seik Phu Taung area. (Table 7, Fig 12,13). The largest GBH trees were *Melanorrhoea glabra* (Thit-si) and *Cryteronia pubescens* (Anan-bo) in Thit Phyu area and *Melanorrhoea glabra* (Thit-si) and *Manglietia insignis* (Taung-sa-ga) in Seik Phu Taung area.

Table.8 Population density of tree species across height class interval

Height Class (m)	Thit Phyu Area			Seik Phu Taung Area		
	Species	Individual	% of Individual	Species	Individual	% of Individual
< 6	63	289	36.629	45	252	31.111
6 ≤ 9	62	188	23.828	42	181	22.346
9 ≤ 12	56	113	14.322	37	133	16.420
12 ≤ 15	41	87	11.027	40	116	14.321
15 ≤ 18	31	67	8.492	32	75	9.259
≥ 18	23	45	5.703	26	53	6.543
Total	103	789	100	86	810	100

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Fig.14. Population density of tree species across height class interval in Thit Phyu Area

Fig.15. Population density of tree species across height class interval in Seik Phu Taung Area

Tree Species Distribution by Frequency Classes

According to the Raunkiaer (1934), five frequency classes of tree species frequency distribution were found in the study area. In the present study, high distribution values were found in lower frequency classes (A and B). Whereas lower values were found in higher frequency classes (C, D and E). (Table 9, Fig 16,17)

Table 9. Tree Species Distribution by Frequency Classes

Frequency Class	Frequency Range	Thit Phyu Area		Seik Phu Taung Area	
		Species	% of Total species	Species	% of Total species
A	1-20%	60	58.252	51	59.302
B	21-40%	28	27.184	18	20.930
C	41-60%	12	11.650	9	10.465
D	61-80%	2	1.942	6	6.977
E	81-100%	1	0.971	2	2.326
Total		103	100	86	100

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Fig.16. Tree species distribution by frequency class in Thit Phyu Area

Fig.17. Tree species distribution by frequency class in Seik Phu Taung Area

Discussions and Conclusions

A total of 126 tree species representing 79 genera and 43 families were analysed in two study sites. As the results of Jackknife estimation, species compositions of Thit Phyu area in all layers were more rich than Seik Phu Taung area. Species diversity was not significantly different in tree and herb layers of both study sites. Only shrub layer, Seik Phu Taung area was more diverse than Thit Phyu area because of shrub species were more evenly distributed in Seik phu Taung area. Among the families recorded, Euphorbiaceae was the dominant one. Floristic compositions of two different study areas were compared by means of coefficient similarity of Sorenson's index. The high similarities among two different sites are understandable, as dominant species were similar in Thit Phyu and Seik Phu Taung area.

Calculations of IVI have helped in understanding the ecological significance of the species in the respective vegetation types. According to ranking important value index in Thit Phyu area and Seik Phu Taung area *Melanorrhoea glabra* Wall. (Thit-si) and *Sapium insigne* Benth. (Taung-kala) were found highest IVI value 31.386%, and 26.743% respectively. So these species could be considered as ecologically representative species of study area. Evaluation of density-dependent status of species in a study site is important for conservation and management of forests. The highest number of species was encountered in the low diameter class $\leq 30\text{cm}$ and height class $< 6\text{m}$. Species number gradually decreased with the fall in the count of stems in higher diameter class and height class category in both sites. One of the reasons for a high density of trees (per/ ha) in lower girth class is that these forests were put under selection system of timber extraction in the past.

In addition, the study area showed that disturbances such as logging, charcoal making and firewood collection were the major destructive force and one of the influencing factors for forest structure. *Melanorrhoea glabra*(Thit-si)and *Cryteronia pubescens* (Anan- bo) *Manglietia insignis* (Taung- sa- ga) were observed as the long life of representative tree species in this study area because they possessed largest diameter and height among the forest trees. In the present study, high distribution value was found in lower frequency classes (A and B) indicating a high degree of floristic heterogeneity (Lamprecht, 1989). It may be concluded that Salu Reserved Forest are still rich in tree species diversity, even after great disturbance to the ecology.

Therefore, special priority should be given to conserve these fragile elements of biodiversity, that are facing pressure from increasing population and developmental activities. This research will recognize the information and phytosociological data of the actual natural vegetation and to develop practical technology for environmental management of forest community in Salu Reserved Forest.

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